

Infectious Waste Management in Household: A Case Study of Khukwang Sub-District, Lat Lum Kaeo District, Pathumthani Province, Thailand

Ketsanee Chubupa, Yanasinee Suma, Numfon Eaktasang

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 27, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: November 29, 2022</p> <p>Keywords : Health-care waste, Infectious waste, Waste management practice</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7378382</p>	<p><i>This study investigated infectious waste management practices at the household level. Data was gathered from 68 households in the study area, with bedridden, kidney, and diabetes patients totaling 28, 3, and 37, respectively. Infectious waste generation and management practices were collected. The results show that the infectious waste generation was 25.281 kg/day with a generation rate of 0.37 kg/patient/day. The composition of sharp and non-sharp wastes was 0.013 kg/day and 25.268 kg/day, respectively. The results of management practices showed that segregation, collection, and storage of infectious waste have not been conducted properly. In addition, the transfer, transportation, and final disposal methods were inadequate due to the obvious lack of a collection route system. The study showed the necessity for training, the provision of knowledge for infectious waste management at the community level and operating the community system for infectious waste management.</i></p>

Introduction

Health-care waste (HCW) is currently increasing, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020-2022 (Sari et al., 2021). The composition of the face mask and antigen testing kits for COVID-19 detection was contained in household waste (PCD, 2022). Lack of proper management of HCW can affect occupational health and the environment, especially infectious waste (Hossain et al., 2011; WHO, 2014; Markkanen et al., 2015). The HCW is composed of hazardous and non-hazardous materials. The World Health Organization (WHO) reported that of the total amount of waste generated by health-care activities, about 85% is general, non-hazardous waste, whereas the remaining 15% is considered hazardous waste that may be infectious, toxic, or radioactive (WHO, 2018). The HCW was categorized into 8 types, including infectious waste, pathological waste, sharp waste, chemical waste, pharmaceutical waste, cytotoxic waste, radioactive waste, and non-hazardous or general waste. The major sources of HCW are hospitals and other health facilities, laboratories, research centers, and nursing homes for the elderly (Neves et al., 2022).

Thailand is a developing country with advanced technology for public health, but the number of patients is still increasing. The HCW management system did not cover all sectors of generation sources, especially in home care. Infectious waste generated in Thailand in 2021 was 90,009.23 tonnes, which increased by about 87.7% when compared to 2020 (47,962 tonnes) because of the COVID-19 situation (PCD, 2022). The majority of infectious waste (98.91%) was generated in hospitals (Office of Natural Resources and Environmental Policy and Planning, 2022). In addition, the pandemic of COVID-19 was found in the generation of waste from sources of infection such as community isolation, hospitals, quarantine facilities, and households where patients were isolated. Approximately 81,774.67 tonnes (90.85%) of infectious waste was appropriated for management by the government and private sector using the incineration method. Due to the scarcity of infectious waste incinerators during the COVID-19 pandemic in Thailand, the double amount of infectious waste was ineffectively managed for disposal methods. To solve the infectious waste management problem, the Ministry of Health (MoH) has announced the rules and regulations for disposing infectious waste in municipal waste incinerators and cement kilns (PCD, 2022).

Infectious waste management in hospitals was collected and disposed of using the incineration method, which controlled environmental pollution such as air pollution and ash. The laws and regulations were mandated for the major sources, like hospital and laboratory research. Home care for the elderly is becoming more common, as is home care for patients with non-communicable diseases. The infectious wastes in households are continuously increasing in Thailand and throughout the world (Ikeda et al., 2021). Lack of awareness about the health hazards related to HCW, inadequate training in proper waste management, and the absence of waste management and disposal systems are the most common problems connected with HCW (Nemathaga et al., 2008; Mascolo et al., 2017). Therefore, infectious waste management in households is interesting to investigate.

The objective of this study was to investigate infectious management at the household level in Pathumthani province, Thailand. Waste generation, composition, and management practices were studied. The data was obtained from 68 households located in Khukwangsub-district, LatLumKaeodistrict, Pathumthani province, Thailand.

Methodology

Data Collection

This study's methodology was based on data and information gathered from 68 households in Khukwangsub-district, LatLumKaeodistrict, Pathumthani province, Thailand. These samples represented households where patients live. The patients in this study were bedridden patients and those with non-communicable diseases (kidney disease and/or diabetes) who generated infectious waste in households. A total of 68 patients' information was obtained from the Health Promoting Hospital of Khukwangsub-district (HDC, 2021). This study was conducted during the period from January to March 2022. The waste sampling was carried out over a one-week period for each home. The waste sample was weighed and prepared properly to determine the infectious waste composition. The waste samples were classified into two categories (Table 1) (Zikhathile et al., 2022). The information on infectious waste management practices was collected using a questionnaire that was approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of Thammasat University (Science) (No. 111/2564). Anonymity was maintained to protect the participant's identities and confidential information. The analysis data was presented as an average value. The questionnaire contained questions including infectious waste management practices (generation of waste and practices related to segregation, collection, storage, transfer and transportation, and final disposal).

Table 1. Classification of Infectious Waste

Types of waste	Composition
Sharp waste	Syringe, needle, blade, etc.
Non-sharp waste	
- Solid	Waste contaminated with blood and other bodily fluids such as gauze, cotton, tissue paper, sanitary pad, plastic tube, saline bag, etc.
- Liquid/solution	Solution contaminated with body fluid such as saline solution, hemodialysis solution, etc.

Data Analysis

Infection waste generation rate was calculated following Equation 1 and presented in kg/patient/day. Waste compositions were analyzed into two categories (sharp and non-sharp wastes) and presented as an average value. The data from the completed questionnaires of 68 households was analyzed and presented as descriptive information.

$$\text{Infectious waste generation rate (kg/patient/day)} = \frac{\text{Total waste generation (kg/day)}}{\text{Number of Patient (patient)}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Results and Discussion

Background Information

A total of 68 households in Khukwangsub-district, LatLumKaeodistrict, Pathumthani province, Thailand, provided infection waste management data. As shown in Table 2, the 68 patients from 68 households were bedridden and non-communicable disease (kidney disease and/or diabetes).

Table 2. Group and Number of Patients in This Study

Group	Number of patient (patient)	Percentage
Bedridden patient	28	41.2
Kidney disease	3	4.4
Diabetes	37	54.4
Total	68	100.0

The personal information of 68 patients was collected using a questionnaire, as presented in Table 3. The majority of patients in this study were aged 61-70 (26.5%); males and females were 39 (57.4%) and 29 (42.6%),

respectively. Educational level was found to be highest in primary school at 36 (52.9%) and followed by high school at 21 (30.9%). Labor was the most common occupation (36.8%), followed by owning a business (14.6%).

Table 3. General Information of Patients in This Study

Information	Number of patient (patient)	Percentage
<i>Age (years)</i>		
≤ 50	11	16.2
51-60	13	19.1
61-70	18	26.5
> 70	26	38.2
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	39	57.4
Female	29	42.6
<i>Educational level</i>		
Primary school	36	52.9
High school	21	30.9
Bachelor's degree and higher	11	16.2
<i>Occupation</i>		
Labor	25	36.8
Own business	14	20.6
Agriculture	9	13.2
Others	20	29.4
N= 68		

Infectious Waste Generation

The total amount of infectious waste generated by 68 patients in Khukwangsub-district, LatLumKaeodistrict, Pathumthani province, Thailand, was 25.281 kg/day. The infectious waste generation rate was calculated to be 0.37 kg/patient/day. The composition of sharp waste and non-sharp waste was 0.013 and 25.268 kg/day, respectively. As a result, the most infectious waste generated in households was non-sharp waste that related to a group of patients. The result of this study was higher than previous research that found a range of 0.012-0.08 kg/patient/day in the community health centers (Oduro-Kwarteng et al., 2021). Otherwise, a previous study in the hospital reported a rate of 0.60 kg/patient/day (Nemathaga et al., 2008), ranging from 0.5-2.2 kg/bed/day (Abdulla et al., 2008), and 0.7-2.92 kg/bed/day (Oduro-Kwarteng et al., 2021).

Composition of Infectious Waste

The infectious waste composition analysis of 68 patients is presented in Figure 1. The compositions of average sharp waste and non-sharp waste were 0.05% and 99.95%, respectively. As a result, the findings were consistent with a previous report on the amount of sharp waste generated in home medical care, which was 1% (Silva et al., 2022). The major contribution of non-sharp waste was hemodialysis solution (65.27%), which was generated by kidney patients during the treatment process. Therefore, the volume of rinse solution was higher when compared to other waste compositions. Additionally, the greatest waste from bedridden patients was produced by sanitary pads, cotton, and tissue paper, at 8.07%, 8.01%, and 5.4%, respectively. As a result, sharp waste was low when compared to the previous study's range of 3.09-5.71% in hospitals, and 12.87-22.19% in health centers (Oduro-Kwarteng et al., 2021). Also, sharp waste was found to be 10% (Abdulla et al., 2008) and 3.28% (Neves et al., 2022), as reported previously. Hospitals generated around 0.86% of liquid waste, whereas no liquid waste was produced at health centers (Oduro-Kwarteng et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Infectious Waste Composition

Infectious Waste Management Practice

Infectious waste management practices related to segregation, collection, storage, transfer and transportation, and final disposal were collected using a questionnaire. Table 4 presents the infectious waste management practices that were obtained from 68 patients. The results show that proper segregation practice by separating infectious waste from general waste in households was approximately 79.4% and the remaining 20.6% was improper separation, such as discharge of the hemodialysis solution directly to the municipal sewer system and mixing of sharp and non-sharp wastes. This study was similar to a previous study that reported that the problem of HCW segregation was lack of knowledge about HCW segregation (Hangulu and Akintola, 2017; Odonkor et al., 2020). The collection by using a plastic bag or container and closing it to prevent contamination or transmission of disease was found to be 85.3% and 14.7% for appropriate and non-appropriate practices, respectively. The majority of the patient was improperly managed (63.2%) in the storage process because of the small amount of waste generation per day; therefore, there was storage over 5 days, whereas the guidelines for infectious waste storage recommended 1-2 days of storage without temperature control. Transfer and transportation practices were 54.4% and 45.6% for proper and improper management, respectively. The health-care service or hospital was located quite far from households, and because of a lack of awareness, some patients were discharged to the general waste collection system of the local authority (Hangulu and Akintola, 2017). In addition, disposal methods were related to transfer and transport practices because the patients followed proper practices. The final disposal methods were operated by the public and private sectors, which followed laws and regulations.

Based on the information obtained from this study, the lack of guidelines and training in infectious waste management among patients or caregivers resulted in the incorrect management of infectious waste. This result was supported by the prior study (Ikeda, 2014; Silva et al., 2022). Furthermore, there are insufficient transfer, transportation, and disposal methods because there is no established collection route for HCW generated on a small scale, as reported previously (Oduro-Kwarteng et al., 2021; Silva et al., 2022). Inadequate medical waste management was found in various developing countries (Udofia et al., 2017).

Table 4. Infectious Waste Management Practices

Management practice	Appropriate practice patient (%)	Non-appropriate practice patient (%)	Details of the assessment ¹
Segregation	54 (79.4%)	14 (20.6%)	Segregation infectious waste from general waste in household, mixed sharp and non-sharp wastes
Collection	58 (85.3%)	10 (14.7%)	Collection by using a plastic bag or container and closing it to prevent contamination or

			transmission of disease
Storage	25 (36.8%)	43 (63.2%)	Put it in a separate area and storage 1-2 days to transfer for disposal
Transfer and transportation	37 (54.4%)	31 (45.6%)	Transfer to a community-based health-care service or hospital, or place in a drop-off location for a local authority service or the private sector
Disposal method	37 (54.4%)	31 (45.6%)	Incineration or other appropriate method of disposal by local authority service or private sector.

[†] The details of the assessment followed the regulations and guidelines of the Ministry of Health, Thailand.
N= 68

Conclusion

This study investigated the infectious waste generation, composition, and management practices in Khukwangsub-district, LatLumKaeodistrict, Pathumthani province, Thailand. The infectious waste generation was 25.281 kg/day with a generation rate of 0.37 kg/patient/day. Most of the infectious waste generated from 68 patients was 0.013 kg/day of sharp waste and 25.268 kg/day of non-sharp waste. The current practices for infectious waste management are not the best practices due to a lack of laws and regulations and an established collection route at the community level. This study suggested that the provision of knowledge for infectious waste management through local authorities could raise household awareness and ensure proper management. Additionally, establishing a collection route for the community's infectious waste collection might ease the challenge of locating a final disposal strategy that is secure for the environment and public health.

Acknowledgements or Notes

This study was funded by the Faculty of Public Health, Thammasat University.

References

- Abdulla, F., Qdais, H.A. & Rabi, A. (2008). Site investigation on medical waste management practices in northern Jordan. *Waste Management*. 28 (2), 450-458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2007.02.035>
- Hangulu, L. & Akintola, O. (2017). Perspectives of policy-makers and stakeholders about health care waste management in community-based care in South Africa: a qualitative study. *BMC Health Services Research*. 17, 290. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-017-2236-x>
- Health Data Center.(2021). Health data of Pathumthani. Health Promoting Hospital. <https://hdcservice.moph.go.th/hdc/main/index.php>
- Hossain, S. Santhanam, A., Norulaini, N.A.N. & Omar, A.K.M. (2011). Clinical solid waste management practices and its impact on human health and environment-A review. *Waste Management*. 31(4), 754-766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2010.11.008>
- Ikeda, Y. (2014). Importance of patient education on home medical care waste disposal in Japan. *Waste Management*. 34(7), 1330-1334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2014.04.017>
- Ikeda, Y., Fujiwara, H. & Sasaki, M. (2021). Is there a difference between urban and rural areas in the disposal of home medical care waste? 13 years of nation-wide repeated cross-sectional study in Japan. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*. 23, 323-329). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-020-01132-0>
- Mascolo, M.D., Espinouse, M.L. and Hajri, A.E. (2017). Planning in Home care structures: A literature review. *IFAC PapersOnLine*. 50(1), 4654-4659. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2017.08.689>
- Markkanen, P., Galligan, C., Laramie, A., Fisher, J. & Sama, S. (2015). Understanding sharps injuries in home healthcare: The safe home care qualitative methods study to identify pathways for injury prevention. *BMC Public Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-015-1673-x>
- Nemathaga, F., Maringa, S. & Chimuka, L. (2008). Hospital solid waste management practices in Limpopo province, South Africa: A case study of two hospitals. *Waste Management*, 28(7), 1236-1245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2007.03.033>
- Neves, A.C., Maia, C.C., de Castro e Silva, M.E., Vimieiro, G.V. & Mol, M.P.G. (2022). Analysis of healthcare waste management in hospitals of Belo Horizonte, Brazil. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 23, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-22113-w>
- Odonkor, S. & Mahami, T. (2020). Healthcare waste management in Ghanaian hospitals: Associated public health and environmental challenges. *Waste Management and Research: The Journal for a Sustainable Circular Economy*. 38(8), 831-839. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X20914748>

- Oduro-Kwarteng, S., Addai, R. & Essandoh, H.M.K. (2021). Healthcare waste characteristics and management in Kumasi, Ghana. *Scientific African*, 12, e00784. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2021.e00784>
- Office of Natural Resources and Environmental Policy and Planning. (2022). Environmental Quality Report 2021. Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment. <https://www.onep.go.th/publication-soe/>
- Pollution Control Department. (2022). Thailand State of Pollution Report 2021. Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment. https://www.pcd.go.th/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/pcdnew-2022-08-26_08-13-23_314008.pdf
- Sari, G.L., Hilmi, I.L., Nurdiana, A., Azizah, A.N. & Kasasiah, A. (2021). Infectious waste management as the effects of COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. *Asian Journal of Social Science and Management Technology*, 3(2), 62-75. <http://www.ajssmt.com/Papers/326275.pdf>
- Silva, T., Silva, M.M., Florencio, L. & Santos, S.M. (2022). A qualitative descriptive case study on home medical waste management in Brazil. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*. 24, 2068-2077. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-022-01462-1>
- Udofia, E.A., Gubriel, G. & Fobil, J. (2017). Solid medical waste: a cross sectional study of household disposal practices and reported harm in Southern Ghana. *BMC Public Health*. 17, 464. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-017-4366-9>
- WHO. (2018). Health-care waste. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/health-care-waste#cms>
- WHO. (2014). Safe management of wastes from health-care activities. 2nd Edition. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241548564>
- Zikhathile, T., Atagana, H., Bwapwa, J. & Sawtell, D. (2022). A review of the impact that healthcare risk waste treatment technologies have on the environment. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 19(19):11967. 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191911967>

Author Information

Ketsanee Chubupa

Faculty of Public Health, Thammasat University
99, M.18, Paholyothin Road, Piyachart Building,
Khlong 1, KhlongLuang, Pathumthani, 12120,
Thailand

Yanasinee Suma

Faculty of Public Health, Thammasat University
(Lampang Campus)
248, M2, Lampang-Chiang Mai Road,
Pongyangkhok,
Hangchat, Lampang, 52190, Thailand

Numfon Eaktasang*

Faculty of Public Health, Thammasat University
99, M.18, Paholyothin Road, Piyachart Building,
Khlong 1, KhlongLuang, Pathumthani, 12120,
Thailand
